

ISic1236

I.Sicily inscription 1236

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 8742

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 14 cm

Width 27 cm

Depth 2 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. □ Θ(εοῖς) □ Κ(αταχθονίοις) □

2. Ὀστρεῖς Λοίνας

3. ἔζησεν □ ἔτη

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493801

EDCS 39101601

PHI 140721

PHI 175623

Bibliography

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